

D4.8

Practice Abstracts - Batch 1

Prepared by F6S

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D4.8 – Practice Abstracts – Batch 1

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Abstract

This document includes a first set of 25 Practice Abstracts that will be developed within the project. The Practice Abstracts cover topics such as the FOODITY components, information on recommendation systems, datasets, standards, and ontologies, information on FOODITY technologies, the photovoice engagement activities, and the first six FOODITY pilots funded from the project's first open call.

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AHD	Attended home delivery
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
B2C	Business to Customer
CSE-TKAS	The Kitchen Adventure: Fostering Behavior Change and Improving Healthy and Sustainable Nutrition Through a Digital App”
DSS	Decision Support System
EcoTrace	Empowering Citizens for Sustainable and Nutritional Food Choices
EEG	Electroencephalogram
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership 'Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability'
FoodMarketMap	Mastering and Recognizing Key Elements of Food Choices to Monitor and Personalise Your Diet
FCB	Food composition database
DAITA	Digital diet assistant for cancer patients and their caregivers
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
LiFR	Lightweight Fuzzy semantic Reasoner
LLM	Large language models
MaOO	Many objective optimization
MATURE	Content-based recommender system
MI4SaferFOOD	Multispectral imaging application for food safety and quality evaluation
ML	Machine Learning
MSI	Multispectral imaging
NAct	Nutrition & Activity Ontology
NFC	Near Field Communication
NVS	Virtual Coaching System
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PA	Practice Abstract
PDT	Personal Digital Twin
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RS	Recommendation systems
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SaaS	Software as a Service
STRADA	Development of a Miniaturised Food Sensor Enhanced with Data-Driven Technology for Efficient Food Management
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
TP	Third Party(ies)
TRBCO	Trajectory Reinforcement-based Bacterial Colony Optimization
VAFA	Visually Aware Food Analysis

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1 Introduction

The present document is deliverable D4.8 – “Practice Abstracts – Batch 1”, framed within “WP4 – Outreach and open calls management” of the FOODITY project.

The **FOODITY project has the objective of delivering 50 Practice Abstracts (PA)** over the course of the project. These are to be delivered in two batches: 25 in batch 1, represented in this document, and 25 in batch 2, to be delivered at the end of the project in December 2025.

A PA can be described as a short summary that provides information, recommendation, or a practice that can be used by different end-users in their daily activities.

The PA developed within the FOODITY project will mainly focus on relevant information collected through research activities, information about the technology developed within the project that can be used by end-users, and information about the projects funded by FOODITY and their respective data-driven solutions.

This **first batch of 25 PA is presented in this deliverable format** for reporting purposes, but will be converted to the traditional EIP-AGRI common format (while keeping the FOODITY visual identity) for broader communication purposes, including on the [FOODITY website](#), the FOODITY [Zenodo community](#), and social media. The format is recommended as it is expected to facilitate the exchange of knowledge and contact between potential partners in innovation projects. Furthermore, it contributes to building up a repository of practical knowledge across the EU via the [EIP-AGRI project database](#).

The present deliverable is structured into three main sections:

1. Introduction, the current section, which provides an overview of the document context.
2. FOODITY Practice Abstracts, which includes the first batch of 25 PA.
3. Final considerations, which summarises the next steps for the first and second batch of PA.

2 FOODITY Practice Abstracts

Table 1 summarises the first batch of 25 practice abstracts that have been developed in the first period of the project. The table also indicates the FOODITY partner (or Third Parties, 'TP') most involved in the preparation of the practice abstract, and the main and second target audiences.

The following possible target audiences were defined and based on the **target groups** defined in the FOODITY project.

- Academia/ RTO/ education *[listed as Research]*
- Citizens
- Food system actors (producers, retailers, distributors)
- Industry (developers of digital solutions) *[listed as Industry]*
- Policy makers
- Representatives of consumers and other groups *[listed as Wider representatives]*

Table 1. Summary of practice abstracts and target audience

Practice Abstract name	Partner responsible	Main target audience	Secondary target audience
Food and nutrition component - Food recognition from photos	CERTH	Food system actors	Research
Food and nutrition component - Food product identification from photo	CERTH	Food system actors	Research
Food and nutrition component - Personalised nutrition plan	CERTH	Food system actors	Research
Food and nutrition component - Personalised support for nutrition/ physical activity	CERTH	Food system actors	Research
Food and nutrition component - Nutrition and activity ontology	CERTH	Food system actors	Research
Nutrition recommendation systems	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Recipe recommendation systems	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Restaurant recommendation systems	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Data collection technologies for food, nutrition, and health	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Online food retail	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Food and nutrition datasets	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Food and nutrition standards	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
Food and nutrition data ontologies	CERTH	Research	Food system actors
DataU - A GDPR compliant cloud-based distributed platform	JIBE	Food system actors	Industry
Data Lake - Food and nutrition data repository	SOF	Citizens	Food system actors
PhotoVoice Methodology	ZSI	Research	Policy makers
PhotoVoice - Citizens' reflections from Austria	ZSI	Research	Citizens
PhotoVoice - Citizens' reflections from Bulgaria	JIBE	Research	Policy makers

Practice Abstract name	Partner responsible	Main target audience	Secondary target audience
PhotoVoice - Citizens' reflections from Portugal	F6S	Citizens	Wider representatives
EcoTrace project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors
CSE-TKAS project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors
DIAITA project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors
MI4SaferFOOD project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors
STRADA project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors
FoodMarketMap project	TP	Citizens	Food system actors

2.1 PA1: Food and nutrition components - Food recognition from photos

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the **food recognition from photos component**, particularly its characteristics, specific formats, functionalities, the mechanisms in which they operate, and the licensing terms under which it can be made available.

Table 2. Characterisation of the food recognition from photos component

Item	Description
What is provided	An AI model ¹ , i.e., a deep learning network that automatically recognises food depicted in a photo.
Component format	A <i>.py</i> (Python) file and <i>.bin</i> (model weights) file.
What it does	Receives as input a photo of food, analyses the photo, and provides as output a probability for each element in a specified list of foods (food titles), to be the depicted food.
How it works	<p>The model is based on a transformer network architecture that splits photos in patches, processes the patches in different scales, produces photo-specific feature vectors, and classifies them into food classes (specific foods).</p> <p>The model has been trained on and evaluated with two publicly available datasets for food recognition: Food-101 and Food2K.</p> <p>The Food-101 dataset consists of 101 food categories with 750 training and 250 test images per category, totalising 101k images.</p> <p>Food2K is a large food recognition dataset with 2,000 categories and over 1 million images.</p>

¹ An AI model is a tool or algorithm which is based on a certain data set through which it can arrive at a decision – all without the need for human interference in the decision-making process.

Item	Description
Technical details/ considerations	<p>The above model has been developed, trained, and tested on the following system requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Hardware (H/W)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ GPU = GeForce RTX 3080 10GB○ RAM = 32 GB○ CPU = i9-10900K● Software (S/W)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Cuda = 11.3○ Cudatoolkit = 11.3.1 <p>It is suggested that at least the above H/W requirements are fulfilled before using the component.</p> <p>Additional to the code, a requirements .txt file for Conda (or similar) will be included so that an appropriate virtual environment can be created.</p> <p>This model has not been tested in any mobile device and therefore for any use of this model on mobile devices candidate developers are responsible to accordingly adapt it.</p>
Related datasets/ standards	<p>The datasets used for the training and test of this model are the Food-101² and Food2K³. They consist of images categorised in 101 categories and 2000 categories respectively. Some of the Food-101 categories are apple_pie, baby_back_ribs, baklava, to give an example, while some of the Food2K categories are Margherita pizza, Black pepper steak, Tonkatsu, to give some examples.</p>
References	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Bossard, L., Guillaumin, M., & Van Gool, L. (2014). Food-101–mining discriminative components with random forests. In Computer Vision–ECCV 2014: 13th European Conference, Zurich, Switzerland, September 6-12, 2014, Proceedings, Part VI 13 (pp. 446-461). Springer International Publishing.2. Min, W., Wang, Z., Liu, Y., Luo, M., Kang, L., Wei, X., ... & Jiang, S. (2023). Large scale visual food recognition. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence.
IPR considerations	<p>The component is provided under the following licence: "Food recognition from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0</p> <p>The Food-101 dataset was introduced in [1]. Further IPR information can be found at: https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dansbecker/food-101.</p> <p>The Food2K dataset was introduced in [2].</p>

² <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/dansbecker/food-101>

³ <http://123.57.42.89/FoodProject.html>

Figure 1. PA1 - Examples of images on the Food2K dataset

Figure 2. PA2 - Examples of images on the Food-101 dataset

2.2 PA2: Food and nutrition components - Food product identification from photo

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the **food product identification from a photo** which is an automatic process of retrieving product information like macronutrients. The component takes as input the barcode of a product in the format of a photo and returns the corresponding information in the form of a json file.

Table 3. Characterisation of the Food product identification from photos component

Item	Description
What is provided	An application that automatically identifies a food product barcode from a photo of the barcode and uses this information to retrieve product information from free online product databases.
Component format	A <i>.py</i> (in the form of a python script) file and <i>.bin</i> (model weights) file.
What it does	Automatically identifies a food product barcode from a photo of the barcode, e.g., photo of a food product, and uses this information to retrieve food product information from free online databases.
How it works	Given an image of a barcode (e.g., photo, screenshot, etc.) the component automatically identifies the barcode and connects to free online databases (e.g., the Open Food Facts database) via the corresponding APIs and retrieves the corresponding product information.
References	The component was based on validated work that has been published (Bossard et al., 2014; Min et al., 2023)
Technical details/ considerations	The requirements of this component are: python 3.6 pip 23.1.2 Additionally, the component needs the following libraries to work: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• requests 2.31.0• pyzbar 0.1.9• PIL 10.0.0
Related datasets/ standards	In the provided implementation the component connects to the Open Food Facts database of food products, which is based on free contributions by users. The database consists of over 2 million products with their corresponding barcode. However, the component can be adjusted to connect to other similar databases. USDA FoodData Central, Nutritionix, Edamam, and Open Menus are some examples of such databases with respective APIs.

Item	Description
IPR considerations	The component is provided under the following marking: "Food product identification from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0

```

code: "8422410133482"
▼ product:
  _id: "8422410133482"
  ▼ _keywords:
    0: "bonpreu"
    1: "maduixa"
    2: "refresc"
  added_countries_tags: []
  additives_old_tags: []
  additives_original_tags: []
  additives_tags: []
  allergens: ""
  allergens_from_ingredients: ""
  allergens_from_user: "(es) "
  allergens_hierarchy: []
  allergens_lc: "es"
  allergens_tags: []
  amino_acids_tags: []
  brands: "bonpreu"
  ▼ brands_tags:
    0: "bonpreu"

```

Figure 3. PA2 - Screenshot of the json file retrieved after calling the Open Food Fact API. In the json file, information regarding a corresponding product's barcode is listed.

2.3 PA3: Food and nutrition components – Personalised nutrition plan

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the **personalised nutrition plan** which is a recommendation system for generating personalised meals for two consecutive weeks based on a user's profile.

Table 4. Characterisation of the personalised nutrition plan component

Item	Description
What is provided	A software component that recommends a weekly nutrition plan tailored to an individual's profile
Component format	In the form of a Docker container
What it does	Receives as input a database of dishes, meals, and user profiles and provides as output a weekly nutrition plan tailored to each user's profile.
How it works	Initially, the software creates a list of candidate daily nutrition plans from the dishes and meals in the database (including kcal, micronutrients, ingredients, and recipes). Then, it considers a user's profile, e.g., height, weight, allergies, dietary preferences etc., and filters out daily nutrition plans based on the user profile restrictions (e.g., specific allergy). Subsequently, based on the user profile information, it calculates the appropriate daily caloric intake for the user and compares it to the caloric content of each daily nutrition plan. From this analysis, it ranks the daily nutrition plans from the most suitable to the least suitable. To ensure variety and avoid repetition, the algorithm also checks for meal diversity. Ultimately, the algorithm produces a personalised list of 7 daily nutrition plans (weekly nutrition plan) that are tailored to the user's specific profile and include diverse options. The component was based on validated research that has been reviewed and published [1].
References	[1] Stefanidis, K.; Tsatsou, D.; Konstantinidis, D.; Gymnopoulos, L.; Daras, P.; Wilson-Barnes, S.; Hart, K.; Cornelissen, V.; Decorte, E.; Lalama, E.; Pfeiffer, A.; Hassapidou, M.; Pagkalos, I.; Argiriou, A.; Rouskas, K.; Hadjidimitriou, S.; Charisis, V.; Dias, S.B.; Diniz, J.A.; Telo, G.; Silva, H.; Bensenousi, A.; Dimitropoulos, K. PROTEIN AI Advisor: A Knowledge-Based Recommendation Framework Using Expert-Validated Meals for Healthy Diets. <i>Nutrients</i> 2022, 14, 4435. https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14204435
Technical details/	The recommendation system for generating meal plans is developed in

Item	Description
considerations	Python 3.6 and integrated in a Django back-end and communicating with a React front-end. Therefore, a call with the corresponding API can trigger the process and return the meal plans.
Related datasets/ standards	To use the component, one needs two databases: a 'dishes' database and a 'meals' database. Below, we describe the schema of the required DBs; Some basic content for filling (some of the required fields of) such databases can be found online at https://zenodo.org/record/7308053 (PROTEIN NAP Database), or from other sources.
IPR considerations	The component is provided under the following licence: "Personalised nutrition plan" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

For the above recommendation system to work, two databases are needed. The first database is the dishes database which consists of the below fields:

- "ID" : The unique identifier of the dish.
- "Name (in local country language)" : Name or short description of the dish.
- "Name (in English)": Name or short description of the dish.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 3-6 year-old child (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 3-6 year-old child (in English)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 7-12 year-old child (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 7-12 year-old child (in English)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 13-15 year-old child (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 13-15 year-old child (in English)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 16-18 year-old child (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child."
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for a 16-18 year-old child (in English)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for a child.
- "Ingredients of a standard portion for an adult (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for an adult.

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- "Ingredients of a standard portion for an adult (in English)": Text to be displayed for the ingredients of a standard portion of the dish for an adult.
- "Recipe (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for the dish recipe.
- "Recipe (in English)": Text to be displayed for the dish recipe.
- "Tip (in local country language)": Text to be displayed for tips associated with the recipe. OPTIONAL
- "Tip (in English)": Text to be displayed for tips associated with the recipe. OPTIONAL
- "Kcal": Kcal of a standard portion of the dish for an adult. Based on column 'M'
- "Protein": Protein (in grams) of a standard portion of the dish for an adult. Based on column 'M'
- "Fat": Fat (in grams) of a standard portion of the dish for an adult. Based on column 'M'
- "Carbohydrates": Carbohydrates (in grams) of a standard portion of the dish for an adult. Based on column 'M'
- "Dish type": The type of the dish.
- "For Autumn": The dish is fine for the period Sept. 23 - Dec. 20.
- "For Winter": The dish is fine for the period Dec. 21 - Mar. 20.
- "For Spring": The dish is fine for the period Mar. 21 - Jun. 20.
- "For Summer": The dish is fine for the period June. 21 - Sept. 22.
- "White meat": The dish contains white meat.
- "Red meat": The dish contains red meat, sausages or cured meat.
- "Pork": The dish contains pork.
- "Fish or seafood": The dish contains fish or seafood.
- "Pulses (Legumes)": The dish contains pulses (legumes).
- "Dairy": The dish contains dairy ingredients.
- "Eggs": The dish contains eggs.
- "Pasta": The dish contains pasta.
- "Rice": The dish contains rice.
- "Tubers": The dish contains tubers.
- "Soups": The dish contains soups.
- "Cereals": The dish contains cereals.
- "Fruit": The dish contains fruit.
- "Nuts": The dish contains nuts.
- "Raw vegetables": The dish contains raw vegetables.
- "Cooked vegetables": The dish contains cooked vegetables.
- "Protein mix": The dish contains a protein mix.
- "Unique": The dish is a unique dish.
- "Semi Unique": The dish is a semi-unique dish.
- "Vegetables for semi": The dish contains vegetables for semi-unique dishes.

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- "Red": The dish contains red vegetables.
- "Green": The dish contains green vegetables.
- "White": The dish contains white vegetables.
- "Yellow": The dish contains yellow/orange vegetables.
- "Purple": The dish contains purple vegetables.
- "Multicolor": The dish contains multi-colour vegetables.
- "No colour": The dish does not contain coloured vegetables.
- "For proposals": The dish is fine for dinner proposals and for non-school day lunch proposals.
- "For school": The dish is served at schools.

The second database is the meals database which consists by the following fields:

- "ID The unique identifier of the dish.
- "Name (in local country language)": Name or short description of the meal.
- "Name (in English)": Name or short description of the meal.
- "Type": The type of the meal.
- "Country": The country at which the meal is aimed.
- "For Autumn": The dish is fine for the period Sept. 1/Nov. 14.
- "For Winter": The dish is fine for the period Nov. 15/Feb. 28.
- "For Spring": The dish is fine for the period Mar. 1/May 14.
- "For Summer": The dish is fine for the period May 15/Aug. 31.
- "Dish ID #1": Compose your meal by selecting 1 up to 10 food IDs from the respective 'Dishes' tab.
- "Dish ID #2"
- "Dish ID #3"
- "Dish ID #4"
- "Dish ID #5"
- "Dish ID #6"
- "Dish ID #7"
- "Dish ID #8"
- "Dish ID #9"
- "Dish ID #10"

It is made clear that the construction and filling of the database is needed by anyone who wishes to use the present component.

2.4 PA4: Food and nutrition components - Personalised support for nutrition/ physical activity

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the **personalised support for nutrition/ physical activity** which provides personalised decision support for healthy diet and physical activity options.

Table 5. Characterisation of the personalised support for nutrition/ physical activity component

Item	Description
What is provided	A knowledge-based, decision support system (DSS) in the form of Software as a Service (SaaS), that prioritises foods/ physical activities according to the personal medical conditions, needs, and preferences of an individual.
Component format	In the form of a github repository
What it does	The system prioritises foods/ physical activities (e.g., in a meal plan, in a restaurant menu, in an activity plan), based on whether they are advised given a user's personal medical conditions, needs and preferences. In addition, it filters out - or can potentially issue an alert - over given foods/ physical activities, when they are not medically advised or even potentially hazardous for a given user.
How it works	Given the NAct ontology, the knowledge based DSS matches a) the semantic profile expressing the nutritional, medical and well-being needs, restrictions and preferences of a user and b) the semantic transcoding of a food's ingredients and/or an activity's properties, to: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Reject foods and/or physical activities that are incompatible with a patient's profile (e.g., would trigger one or more of their allergies or are restricted by doctors due to a medical condition).2. Prioritise foods and/or physical activities based on the user's personal needs, conditions and/or preferences. For instance, a deficiency may require an increase in the intake of a certain nutrient, or a medical condition may mandate uptake of a particular type of exercise. All factors in the user's personal profile contribute simultaneously to the final prioritisation score of each food/activity. The component was based on validated research that has been reviewed and published [1].
References	[1] Stefanidis, K.; Tsatsou, D.; Konstantinidis, D.; Gymnopoulos, L.; Daras, P.; Wilson-Barnes, S.; Hart, K.; Cornelissen, V.; Decorte, E.; Lalama, E.; Pfeiffer, A.; Hassapidou, M.; Pagkalos, I.; Argiriou, A.; Rouskas, K.; Hadjidimitriou, S.; Charisis, V.; Dias, S.B.; Diniz, J.A.; Telo, G.; Silva, H.; Bensenousi, A.; Dimitropoulos, K. PROTEIN AI Advisor: A Knowledge-Based Recommendation Framework Using Expert-Validated Meals for Healthy

Item	Description
	Diets. Nutrients 2022, 14, 4435. https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14204435
Technical details/ considerations	The above reasoner is based on LiFR. LiFR (Lightweight Fuzzy semantic Reasoner) is a fuzzy extension of the Pocket KRHyper reasoner, initially designed for first-generation mobile devices. Built on the hyper-tableaux calculus, LiFR performs first-order model generation and translates Description Logic (DL) axioms into first-order clauses. It extends Pocket KRHyper to handle fuzziness, incorporating semantics and transformations for fuzzy operators. LiFR has improved efficiency and disjunction handling, making it suitable for limited-resource devices. It offers inferencing services such as consistency checking, satisfiability checking, concept subsumption, fuzzy entailment, and calculation of the Best Entailment Degree (BED). By generating models satisfying the fuzzy knowledge base, LiFR natively supports computing the BED for various combinations of individuals and concepts.
Related datasets/ standards	For related datasets and standards see Component #5 Nutrition and activity ontology
IPR considerations	The component is provided under the following licence: “Personalised support for nutrition/physical activity” © 2023 by Dorothea Tsatsou, Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is licensed under GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0

Figure 4. PA4 - Mechanism of the Knowledge-based DSS.

2.5 PA5: Food and nutrition components – Nutrition and activity ontology

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the nutrition and activity ontology which is the **Nutrition and Activity Ontology (NAct)**. A deterministic system based on European standards for nutrition, diet, allergies, diseases, and more.

Table 6. Characterisation of the nutrition and activity ontology component

Item	Description
What is provided	An Ontology, i.e., a formal expert model, of nutritional, medical, and lifestyle factors that affect healthy living.
Component format	In the form of a Web Ontology Language (OWL) project.
What it does	It comprises an amalgamation of European guidelines relevant to nutrition and well-being. It also includes experts' evidence-based knowledge, pertaining to foods and their relation to nutrients as well as to foods/physical activities and their well-being consequences, restrictions, and specific goals relevant to user conditions. It can be used to coalesce nutritional, medical, behavioural and lifestyle indicators with potential dietary and physical activity directives.
How it works	NAct ontology is used by the knowledge-based decision support system (DSS) as: a) the finite vocabulary to describe the nutritional, medical and lifestyle characteristics of users (user profiling), as well as the nutritional and lifestyle attributes of foods and activities, and b) the axiomatic backbone by which the knowledge-based DSS infers personalized decisions for any user profile, given the attributes of available foods/activities. Since it comprises a standard ontology, modelling vast information over the healthy living domain, it may also be employed by any means of semantic technology (e.g., inference engine, query engine, semantic classifier, etc.) to retrieve information over such factors and/or drive inference for different contexts in the healthy living domain. The component was based on validated research that has been reviewed and published [1].
References	[1] Neuhaus, F., & Brodaric, B. (2022, January). Nact: The nutrition & activity ontology for healthy living. In <i>Formal Ontology in Information Systems: Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference (FOIS 2021)</i> (Vol. 344, p. 129). IOS Press. [2] McCance, R. A., & Widdowson, E. M. (2014). <i>McCance and Widdowson's the Composition of Foods</i> . Royal Society of Chemistry. [3] Ainsworth, B. E., Haskell, W. L., Herrmann, S. D., Meckes, N., Bassett Jr, D. R., Tudor-Locke, C., ... & Leon, A. S. (2011). 2011 Compendium of Physical Activities: a second update of codes and MET values. <i>Medicine & science in</i>

Item	Description
	<p>sports & exercise, 43(8), 1575-1581.</p> <p>[4] Fernández-López, M., Gómez-Pérez, A., & Juristo, N. (1997). Methontology: from ontological art towards ontological engineering.</p> <p>[5] Peroni, S., Shotton, D. M., & Vitali, F. (2012). Making Ontology Documentation with LODE. In I-SEMANTICS (Posters & Demos) (pp. 63-67).</p>
Technical details/ considerations	<p>NAct is an OWL ontology, falling in the OWL 2 RL expressivity fragment. Additionally, it has been engineered using the protégé ontology editor. NAct is available under a persistent PURL URI . It is published on GitHub, in a dedicated project and repository , while the ontology specification and documentation (LODE [5] version) web page will be permanently maintained through GitHub pages.</p>
Related datasets/ standards	<p>The above ontology is the Nutrition & Activity Ontology (NAct). NAct has been constructed based on European nutritional standards. More specifically the ontology is based on the works of McCance and Widdowson food database [2] and the Compendium of Physical Activities [3], which were deemed by the domain experts as the most vast and most adequate databases adhering to European nutritional, health, and well-being standards.</p> <p>Additionally, the standards of component's 5 ontology is based on the Methontology [4] methodology pertaining to the seven stages: specification, knowledge acquisition, conceptualisation, integration, implementation, evaluation and documentation.</p>
IPR considerations	<p>The component is provided under the following marking: "Food product identification from photo" © 2023 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL), Information Technologies Institute (ITI), Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0</p>

Figure 5. PA5 - The top-level hierarchy of the NAct ontology.

2.6 PA6: Nutrition recommendation systems

A **nutrition recommendation system** is a technology that uses personal and contextual data to provide individuals with personalised nutrition advice. These systems are **designed to improve health outcomes by helping individuals make informed food choices** that align with their specific dietary needs and preferences.

The use of nutrition recommendation systems has shown to have a positive impact on health outcomes, including weight loss and improved blood sugar control. However, there are still challenges to be addressed in the development of these systems, including the need for more accurate and reliable data inputs, as well as the need for more user-friendly interfaces that can be easily integrated into daily life.

A selection of the many researched features being explored for nutrition recommendation systems include:

- Ranking framework that identifies the most appropriate nutrition plan for an individual while considering multiple personal factors such as age, weight, and other pertinent information. Optimisation features to evaluate and rank all feasible nutrition plans based on their compatibility with the individual [1].
- Advanced image processing techniques to estimate the nutrient content of meals based on the portion of nutrients present in their recently consumed meals. This is achieved by capturing RGBD images before and after a meal, followed by image segmentation and volume estimation performed by a neural network [2].
- A heuristic optimization-based recommendation model that uses trajectory reinforcement-based bacterial colony optimization (TRBCO) and a bio-inspired optimization algorithm that mimics the behaviour of bacterial colonies to optimise the accuracy and diversity of the recommendation system [3].
- Electroencephalogram (EEG) signals and a hierarchical ensemble machine learning model to analyse brain responses to a meal and determine if it is palatable. To construct the personalised meal recommendation, the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is applied, which is a multi-criteria decision-making technique that considers the user's preferences and nutritional requirements. Furthermore, a 1-D bin packing algorithm is used to plan menus and ensure that recommended meals fit within the user's dietary restrictions [4].
- DNA data that is analysed using bioinformatic pipelines, coupled with a genetic interpretation database to interpret the results. This is used together with physical examination data and lifestyle data that is evaluated using a questionnaire, which contributes to generating a personalised nutrition model [5].
- Personal Digital Twin (PDT), which can support improved decision-making and treatment, and therefore provide valuable insights for personalised healthcare [6].
- Ontology models in the food domain that provide appropriate food recommendations to individuals based on their health conditions [7].

- Content-based recommender system (MATURE) that incorporates information related to the user and food items to provide recommendations that meet user's specific requirements [8].
- Many objective optimization (MaOO) models contain four different objectives, including user preferences, nutritional values, dietary diversity, and user diet patterns [9].

The aforementioned examples showcase innovation in the development of nutrition recommendation systems that aim to improve people's health by providing personalised and appropriate dietary advice. The examples address technologies such as ontologies, recommender systems, and deep convolutional neural networks to classify food items, estimate calorie requirements, and recommend diets based on nutrient values, user preferences, and health conditions.

A common challenge with nutrition recommendation systems is the need for accurate data to train the models and create the ontology. This can be a time-consuming and laborious process, especially when considering the vast amount of food and nutrient information available. Furthermore, there is a need for standardisation in food labelling and measurement to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the data.

As technology continues to advance, more sophisticated and accurate systems will likely be developed to cater to the diverse dietary needs of individuals. However, it is important to consider the ethical implications of such systems and ensure that they do not contribute to the exacerbation of existing societal inequalities.

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2.7 PA7: Recipe recommendation systems

There has been an increased interest in using recommendation systems to promote healthier eating habits. These systems use large recipe datasets and nutritional information to generate personalised recipe recommendations for individuals. **These recommendation systems aim to adapt recipes based on an individual's specific nutritional needs, allergies, and other preferences.**

A selection of the many researched features being explored for recipe recommendation systems include:

- A model that customises personalised balanced diets based on the limitations of food type and meal cost, using the Hungarian algorithm to establish an objective function for cost. The system uses integer planning to extract a weekly meal plan based on a user's nutritional needs and food restrictions [1].
- The Visually Aware Food Analysis (VAFA) system, which uses the ATNet and PiNet deep learning models, classifies food items and recommends recipes based on an individual's nutritional requirements and preferences. ATNet achieves state-of-the-art performance in food classification, while PiNet outperforms existing methods in recipe recommendation precision [2].
- The Virtual Coaching System (NVS) that recommends recipes based on an ontology between a user's preferences and foods. This system focuses on personalising the generation of recipe recommendations according to a user's allergies, eating habits, lifestyles, and nutritional values [3].
- A system that plans multiple meals using recipes, limiting recommendations to tasteful and culturally acceptable food combinations. The system considers an individual's food preferences, restrictions, and nutritional needs to generate plans for three consecutive weeks [4].

The aforementioned examples showcase innovation in the development of new approaches to customising recipe recommendations based on individual preferences, restrictions, and nutritional requirements. The examples address techniques and technologies such as KNN, Euclidean distance, integer programming, deep learning models, ontology, and knowledge graphs.

A commonality among the examples presented is the personalisation of recipe recommendations based on a user's nutritional needs and food preferences. However, they differ regarding the specific features and constraints they consider, such as allergies, meal cost, and cultural acceptability.

Challenges with recipe recommendation systems include developing effective recommendation systems for healthy eating. For example, one particular difficulty is the collection and processing of large datasets of recipes and nutritional information. Another challenge is ensuring that the recommended recipes align with a user's cultural and taste preferences, making it more likely for them to adopt the recommendations and sustain healthy eating habits.

Future research could focus on the challenges identified in the examples provided and developing more effective and personalised recommendation systems for promoting healthy eating habits.

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2.8 PA8: Restaurant recommendation systems

With the vast amount of data accessible online and the utilisation of data-driven methods, there exists the potential to create recommendation systems (RSs) capable of suggesting restaurants or particular menu items tailored to users' preferences and nutritional requirements. These systems, offering personalised recommendations, have the capacity to assist users in making informed choices when selecting food, thus fostering healthier eating habits.

A selection of the many researched features being explored for restaurant recommendation systems include:

- The AI-powered personalised restaurant menu decoder app proposed in [1] assists users in selecting meals from any restaurant menu by prioritising menu items based on individual preferences and concerns. Utilising a vast dataset of restaurant menus and AI algorithms, the app analyses the nutritional content of each item to provide personalised recommendations tailored to the user's dietary needs and preferences.
- The "meals–plates exploration cycle" recommendation system, as outlined in [2], enriches dining experiences by aiding users in selecting the most fitting plates for their meals. Leveraging machine learning for plate shape estimation and text classification, this system utilises data from the Cookpad recipe dataset and e-commerce platforms to establish meal-plate relationships, catering to user preferences and characteristics of each meal and plate.

In conclusion, the use of data-driven approaches in restaurant RSs for personalised nutrition can have significant benefits. This is a promising area for future research.

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2.9 PA9: Data collection technologies for food, nutrition, and health

To ensure the effectiveness of recommendation systems, various methods and technologies are employed to gather data, primarily somatometric data such as age, height, and weight, as well as additional information like images, heart rate, and sleep data. **Devices utilised for data extraction include:**

- Wearable sensing devices like activity trackers or smartwatches, capable of retrieving vital data such as heart rate and activity type. For instance, the research outlined in [1] showcases the NutriTrek biosensor's ability to continuously analyse sweat for metabolites and nutrients, enabling real-time monitoring of nutritional needs via wireless communication.
- Cameras, integrated into smartphones or activity trackers, can also contribute to recommendation systems by capturing images. For example, innovative techniques discussed in [2] utilise advanced image processing methods to accurately assess nutrient content in RGBD images captured before and after meals.
- Smartphones and applications play a significant role in collecting personal data, offering a user-friendly interface and incorporating gamification to enhance recommendation system interaction.
- Other sensing devices, such as DNA kits, albeit more challenging to use, provide specific data. In [3], researchers utilise EEG signals to extract brain data for recommendation systems, while [4] employs DNA kits to gather genetic information from users.

In conclusion, while advanced non-wearable sensing devices provide invaluable health and nutrition insights, their utilisation involves a complex process of data acquisition, analysis, and application compared to wearable sensors. Challenges such as the need for specialised facility visits, device complexity, and cost may impede their widespread adoption. Streamlining the user experience and reducing complexity and cost could improve the accessibility and effectiveness of non-wearable sensing devices in health and nutrition monitoring.

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2.10 PA10: Data-driven solutions for online food retail

Data-driven innovation technologies have significantly transformed the online food retail industry, enhancing productivity, food safety, and personalised shopping experiences. From optimising yield productivity and quality control at the producer level using ML, AI, and IoT technologies, to ensuring food safety during transportation with IoT sensors, and providing personalised shopping recommendations based on individual preferences and purchase histories, these technologies revolutionise the entire supply chain. The integration of data-driven approaches offers vast opportunities for future advancements, promising increased efficiency, improved food safety, and enhanced consumer satisfaction in the industry.

The field of online food retail and the data-driven technologies that are used can be divided into four subcategories.

- Food supply chain encompasses all activities from agriculture and production to retail, including intermediary steps such as raw material storage and transportation. Data-driven innovations such as RFID tags, IoT sensors, and blockchain technology are employed in the food supply chain to ensure traceability and enhance food safety. For instance, [1] propose a system integrating machine learning and blockchain to automate anomaly detection and prevention, highlighting potential for further research in prevention and cause analysis.
- B2C e-commerce platforms facilitate transactions between producers and customers in the online food retail sector, utilising technologies such as smart storage systems and targeted advertisements to improve efficiency and expand reach. Additionally, customers benefit from personalised product recommendations, exemplified by [2], which proposes a personalised recommendation system within the product subsystem, emphasising the role of data-driven innovation in enhancing user experience and personalised recommendations on e-commerce platforms.
- Recommendation systems in online food retail utilise ML and AI to suggest products based on customer preferences, evolving to incorporate advanced technologies like AR and VR. For instance, [3] propose a novel method for personalised recommendations in physical stores by integrating online shopping behaviour and physical location data, contributing to data-driven innovation and enhancing the customer experience across online and physical retail environments.
- Food delivery research is rapidly growing, fueled by the adoption of data-driven technologies like smart packaging and NFC for package tracking. Real-time order arrival estimation algorithms are crucial for optimising production and ensuring customer satisfaction. [4] propose a framework for demand management in attended home delivery (AHD), emphasising the need to balance customer preferences and profitability. They advocate for data-driven innovation, particularly prescriptive analytics, to enhance service efficiency. The study identifies research gaps and suggests exploring new objectives and business models to improve AHD services, highlighting the potential of data-driven innovation to enhance strategic demand management and the overall delivery experience.

In summary, the literature highlights the significant impact of data-driven innovation technologies on online food retail, leading to remarkable outcomes, innovations, and intelligent solutions. With exponential growth in this research field, the integration of more innovative technologies is anticipated, positioning it as one of the most lucrative areas in the food systems industry.

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2.11 PA11: Food and nutrition datasets

To enable the effective functioning of the data-driven technologies for personalised nutrition and online retail, the availability of data is imperative. However, **a major obstacle in data-driven innovations in the domain of personalised nutrition and food retail is the paucity of sufficiently accurate and valid data.** The dataset categories extracted from the literature review are:

- Food composition datasets provide data on the nutritional and chemical content of foods, including macronutrients, micronutrients, and other bioactive compounds, serving as vital resources for nutrition assessment, research, and food product development.
- Food environmental footprint datasets encompass comprehensive information regarding the environmental impact of food production, including factors like greenhouse gas emissions, water usage, land utilisation, and other sustainability indicators.
- Food price datasets contain detailed data on the cost and pricing of various food products and ingredients.
- Food recipes and menus datasets encompass a wide range of culinary information, including ingredients, preparation methods, and nutritional content. These datasets are invaluable for data-driven solutions in the realm of food and nutrition enabling individuals, food services, and health professionals to create and analyse recipes and menus that align with dietary goals, preferences, and nutritional requirements.
- Food products datasets provide comprehensive information about food items available in the market. These datasets are essential for data-driven solutions in the field of food and nutrition, offering data on ingredients, nutritional content, labelling information, and more.
- Food images datasets consist of collections of food-related images that have been labelled or annotated with information such as food types, portion sizes, and calorie counts. They enable the development of image recognition algorithms, mobile apps, and tools that can help users track their dietary intake, make healthier food choices, and manage portion sizes.
- Eating video datasets contain video recordings that capture individuals eating meals or snacks, often annotated with information about food choices, portion sizes, and eating behaviours.

Eating datasets from wearable sensors consist of data collected through sensors worn by individuals to monitor their eating habits. These datasets include information on chewing patterns, eating duration, and even physiological responses to food consumption.

2.12 PA12: Food and nutrition standards

Food and nutrition **standards are essential for ensuring the safety, quality, and transparency of the food supply while promoting optimal nutrition and health outcomes.** They encompass guidelines and regulations governing various aspects of the food industry, including composition, labelling, and dietary recommendations. By establishing criteria for nutrient content and labelling requirements, these standards empower consumers to make informed choices, support public health initiatives, and guide policymakers in regulatory decisions, ultimately contributing to the well-being of individuals and populations. Food and nutrition standards can be divided into the following categories:

- Food composition standards ensure accuracy in reporting nutritional content, aiding dietary analysis and labelling.
- Standards for food products ensure informative labelling, promoting food safety and transparency for consumers.
- Dietary reference values guide nutrient intake for diverse population groups, informing nutritional goals and policy decisions.
- Guidelines for diet and physical activity promote optimal health and prevent chronic diseases through evidence-based recommendations.
- Food safety management standards maintain safety and hygiene throughout food production, processing, and distribution.
- School food standards promote nutritious meals and healthy eating habits among students in educational settings.
- Microbiology standards ensure food safety by monitoring and controlling microbiological hazards.
- Fisheries and aquaculture standards ensure sustainability, welfare, and quality of aquatic products.
- Essential oil standards ensure purity, safety, and authenticity of essential oil products.
- Starch and by-product standards specify quality and application requirements for starch-based materials.

In summary, food and nutrition standards are vital for ensuring food safety, quality, and transparency while promoting optimal health outcomes. These standards cover aspects such as composition, labelling, and dietary recommendations, empowering consumers, supporting public health initiatives, and guiding policy decisions. From accurate labelling to sustainable practices, food and nutrition standards contribute to the well-being of individuals and populations.

2.13 PA13: Food and nutrition data ontologies

Ontologies function as a form of **standardisation for data representation and interoperability**, providing several key benefits:

- Data interoperability: by establishing standard terms and relationships, ontologies facilitate data exchange between different systems.
- Consistent data modelling: ontologies offer structured frameworks for modelling data, ensuring uniformity and coherence in representation.
- Semantic integration: they enable linking of concepts across different domains, enhancing the depth and relevance of data analysis.
- Data integration and interchange: ontologies support seamless integration of diverse data sources by providing formal representations and enabling mapping between formats.
- Domain-specific standards: some ontologies serve as domain-specific standards, offering widely accepted frameworks for data representation and knowledge sharing within specific communities or industries.

Some ontologies are:

- The following tables list some ontologies [1].
- FoodOn [2].
- ONS [3].
- FOBI [4].
- Crop Dietary Nutrition Ontology (CDNO) [5].
- Ontology for Nutritional Epidemiology (ONE) [6].
- Food Interactions with Drugs Evidence Ontology (FIDEO) [7].
- Food Ontology (FOKB) [8].
- HeLiS [9].

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2.14 PA14: dataU - A GDPR compliant cloud-based distributed platform

The dataU is a GDPR compliant cloud-based distributed platform for secure data-sharing which allows full control over data, who it is being shared with, and the duration. The service can be used in the context of sharing data between citizens (data owners) and third-party services (data processors), or alternatively between two companies, in accordance with their non-disclosure agreements.

DataU is viable in cases where there is personal or sensitive information involved, which requires permission to share and has a high level of trust and confidentiality. **The platform serves as a communication layer between the parties using blockchain technology and does not store the data but grants and revokes access to it, and as such can be treated as a consent management platform.** The storage of the data is therefore facilitated by the data processors, for as long as the data owners have granted. The benefit for both parties is that the permissions are traceable and fully open to all parties involved.

Figure 6. PA14 - Different options available through use of the dataU.

The sharing of data is done in an encrypted, fully distributed, and decentralised manner, utilising the nodeU application, which exposes an API through which consent handling is realised. Data transport is done using an application that runs on the data processor's premises (proxyU), which is responsible for setting up a peer-to-peer, secure tunnel to another proxyU after verifying the correct authentication, authorisation, and other parameters through a nodeU instance.

Both data processors and data owners are identified using their public keys, and verified using a certificate, which is included in every dataU application for the chain of trust to be validated. Data owners interact with dataU through a client application but there is, by design, no single mandatory application.

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Instead, nodeU exposes an API through which web-based dashboards or native mobile or desktop applications can be developed.

Figure 7. PA14 - Visual representation of dataU application in terms of data flow between different processors.

2.15 PA15: Data lake – Food and nutrition data repository

The [FOODITY data lake](#) is a **centralised repository, granting stakeholders and researchers easy access to data while ensuring scalability and reliability in storage**. Its dashboard creation feature offers valuable insights, empowering users to glean meaningful information.

The data lake **encourages collaboration** by connecting various entities, such as food enthusiasts and chefs, with businesses seeking innovations. **All the data uploaded to the data lake adheres to GDPR compliance**, ensuring citizen protection whilst enabling valuable insights for applications in areas including business intelligence and analytics.

Data providers can submit data to the data lake. Before sharing datasets, providers must register on the [website](#), complete their profiles, and provide metadata for their datasets. The access to the website is secured using advanced technology that ensures data privacy, prevents unauthorised access, and empowers data providers with control over their datasets.

For datasets containing personal or sensitive information, such as identifiable data, [dataU](#) (the FOODITY data consent management platform), comes into play to ensure that user consent is obtained before any data sharing occurs. On the other hand, non-personal data can be published directly on the data lake, streamlining the process for datasets that do not require explicit user consent through DataU. To ensure GDPR compliance, data providers must follow data anonymisation, pseudonymisation, and minimisation guidelines, among others.

The **data lake is accessible freely through the dedicated [website](#)**. Authentication is not required for accessing public information about data providers and their datasets.

Figure 8. PA15 - Visual representation of the datalake for data provider and citizen users.

2.16 PA16: Photovoice methodology

In the FOODITY project, the Photovoice methodology is **applied to identify and reflect on citizens' perceptions of data privacy and data sovereignty regarding food and nutrition data**, and to empower citizens regarding data sharing while keeping control of their personal nutrition and health data.

Through this in-depth engagement process, information collected is complemented with state-of-the art knowledge in the domains of food and nutrition and the link with data privacy and data sovereignty.

The Photovoice methodology aims to facilitate empowerment. Initially applied in photojournalism, photovoice empowers people to inform others and to participate in decisions regarding their own lives or their communities' development.

The Photovoice methodology was created by Caroline Wang and Mary Ann Burris with the objectives of (1) enabling people to record and reflect their community's strengths and concerns, (2) promoting critical dialogue and knowledge about issues through group discussions of photographs, and (3) to reaching policy makers⁴⁵.

Therefore, a photovoice workshop is a tool to give people a voice, to engage people who often do not have the opportunity to share their views or to influence decisions⁶ and it is an empowerment tool, as all participants can tell their stories from their perspective and in their way.

In the framework of a photovoice workshop, participants are “asked to represent their personal point of view or opinion by photographing scenes relevant” to them or their community. Thus, it is very important to provide a carefully defined research question to start the photovoice process.

The specificity of a photovoice method is the active role of the participants: respondents determine which subjects are in the photographs and explain them; they introduce subjects that are important for them in relation to a question. The photograph is part of a communication and interpretation process that is continued in the group process.

Within the FOODITY project, this methodology enabled:

- Supporting a bottom-up empowerment process in three FOODITY hubs (Austria, Bulgaria, Portugal).
- Raising awareness on the topics of food and nutrition and the relation with data privacy and data sovereignty and reaching out to a larger group by giving individuals a voice and preparing exhibitions with results.
- Collecting qualitative insights related to the perception and understanding of data privacy and sovereignty by citizens participating in the workshops run in the three FOODITY hubs.

⁴ Wang C, Burris MA. Photovoice: concept, methodology, and use for participatory needs assessment. *Health Educ Behav.* 1997 Jun;24(3):369-87. doi: 10.1177/109019819702400309. PMID: 9158980.

⁵ Budig, K., Diez, J., Conde, P. et al. Photovoice and empowerment: evaluating the transformative potential of a participatory action research project. *BMC Public Health* 18, 432 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-5335-7>

⁶ <https://interfaithphotovoice.org/ifpv-blog/2021/11/3/the-gifts-of-empathy-and-empowerment>

In the context of FOODITY and the activities of the three hubs, the methodology was prepared into a clear set of guidelines that each hub organiser used. The guidelines included general introduction to the methodology, specific instructions on how to implement the process, practical tools to facilitate the implementation (e.g. check-lists and other necessary materials), and further guidance to enable a comparison of processes and results between the three hubs.

The specific structure of the photovoice workshop applied at the FOODITY hubs included:

- **Session 1 (Day 1)**
 - General introduction
 - Initial exercise using pictures
 - Introduction to the topic and presentation of the research question
 - Explanation of the photovoice process.
- **Inter-session activity:** *Field work where participants take a defined number of photos related to the research question.*
- **Session 2 (Day 2)**
 - Group reflection about the photo taking exercise
 - Group dialogue and analysis around the photos, coding the photos and finding clustering them based on similarities.
 - Group discussion and finding common themes.
- **Inter-session activity:** *Workshop organisers/ moderators analyse the contents of the photos according to their symbology, composition, and theorise on their significance.*
- **Session 3 (Day 3)**
 - Presentation of the analysis carried out by the organisers/ moderators.
 - Discussion of the results presented.
 - Creative session to discuss how to exhibit results of the workshop.

2.17 PA17: Photovoice workshop results - Austria hub

The Austria hub photovoice workshop was held in Vienna and brought together a diverse group of eight participants. An equal number of female and male participants made up the group, ranging in age from 21 to 60 and coming from various professional backgrounds. The group was also a mix of local residents and individuals with a migration background.

Based on the common FOODITY Photovoice workshop approach, **six key themes emerged from the discussions, reflecting the participants' thoughts and concerns:**

- **Theme 1 - Awareness raising and education:** Participants acknowledged a lack of awareness about the entire food value chain and the need for critical questioning regarding healthy and ecologically sustainable nutrition. Participants emphasised the importance of starting awareness-raising efforts from childhood and making cultural and ancient knowledge about nutrition accessible to all. There was an appeal to create guidance for healthy nutrition and its production and preparation.
- **Theme 2 - Knowledge exchange:** Participants expressed distrust of labels like [Nutri-score](#) and emphasised the need for transparent and trustworthy product labelling that covers the entire production chain. Participants wish to have more access to information using existing channels, such as screens in doctor's offices, meaning that information should be accessible in the places that are often attended by people. Participants stressed the importance of transparency regarding food, personal data collection, and the availability of honest offers that allow for informed choices, since often essential information is lost due to advertising. Participants also requested for clarity on whether a certain food is regional and seasonal.
- **Theme 3 - Health:** Health was identified as a central and significant topic. Participants emphasised the importance of food diversity, affordable healthy food, and making healthy food look appetising and taste good. There was also recognition that there is no *one-size-fits-all* health dogma, and defining what is healthy and unhealthy can be complex.
- **Theme 4 - Self-determination/ autonomy:** Participants highlighted the tension between freedom and regimentation, with concerns about the potential over-regulation and loss of personal responsibility through data analysis. Participants expressed a desire to retain personal autonomy and data security. They expressed the need to feel safe and unharmed even when their decisions regarding data privacy deviates from official recommendations or guidelines.
- **Theme 5 - Framework for data collection:** Participants identified data collection as a powerful tool that can positively affect people's lives when used responsibly and securely. Participants expressed distrust of data collectors and emphasised the need for clear ownership of data and secure mechanisms to protect it. There was recognition that sharing nutritional data may require sharing sensitive information, but aggregating individual data can lead to a better understanding of the bigger picture. Participants believe that data can be a powerful tool for societal changes once the secure institution and locking mechanisms for data are in place.

- **Theme 6 - Networking/ cross-linking:** Participants discussed the need to draw clear lines between data sharing and personal privacy, with an emphasis on individual choice and consent. However, they still question and do not have an answer as to who would be most suitable in deterring these 'borders'. Bubbles and networks were acknowledged as sources of both security and fragility. Participants highlighted the importance of building communities for secure data sharing and fostering trust within those communities.

2.18 PA18: Photovoice workshop results - Bulgaria hub

The Bulgaria hub photovoice workshop was held in Sofia and brought together a group of nine participants, five male and four female. The participants, with ages spanning from their mid-20s to late 50s, came from diverse professional backgrounds and included both native Bulgarians and foreign expats from Belgium and England.

Based on the common FOODITY Photovoice workshop approach, **four key themes emerged from the discussions, reflecting the participants' thoughts and concerns:**

- **Theme 1 - Misuse:** Participants mentioned that some photos taken only capture partial scenes, reflecting occasional issues with personalised data usage. Images where crowds are visible symbolised the vast data collected, which raised concerns about transparency and potential misuse. The discussions underscored the importance of responsible data handling and clearer communication to build trust and address data-related apprehensions.
- **Theme 2 - Smart use of data:** Participants noted a predominant focus on the technical mechanics of data collection and manipulation, like QR codes, which somewhat detracted from the human-centred dimension of data use. This highlighted the importance of acknowledging people's roles in shaping responsible data practices. The diverse indoor and outdoor photo settings symbolised data's ubiquity in different contexts, showcasing its impact on daily life.
- **Theme 3 - Confusion:** Participants highlighted that the visual content of the photos, including numerous items, conveyed a sense of abundance and variety of choices. The unconventional angles and slight blurriness of the images suggested the challenges individuals face when making decisions, leading to feelings of confusion. The visible labels in the photos underscored the overwhelming amount of data and information present, often inaccessible to the average person who lacks understanding of its significance. The organised layout of the supermarket suggested a potential need for structured guidance and education on food and nutrition, aiming to empower individuals to make informed and healthy choices.
- **Theme 4 - Education:** The coherence among the photos in terms of timing, location, environment, and subject matter (food and people) underscores a unified call for increased education on the subject. The inclusion of children in some photos, along with the presence of food, suggests the importance of early engagement with food and nutrition education to address parental uncertainties regarding how to provide the best guidelines for their children.

2.19 PA19: Photovoice workshop results - Portugal hub

The Portugal hub photovoice workshop was held in Coimbra and gathered seven participants, two men and five women, ranging in age from 24 to 58. and coming from various professional backgrounds. The group was also a mix of local residents and individuals with a migration background. All participants had at least a master's degree, the majority with PhD or concluding a PhD. Their educational background included anthropology, engineering, economics and psychology. Several participants had experiences with EU-funded projects.

Based on the common FOODITY Photovoice workshop approach, **10 key themes emerged from the discussions, reflecting the participants' thoughts and concerns:**

- **Theme 1 – Ethics:** Participants highlighted the significance of ethics in data management. They stressed that ethical responsibilities must be upheld by both consumers of goods and services and those delivering them. This underscores the need for collective commitment to conducting processes in an ethical and conscientious manner.
- **Theme 2 - Control and supervision:** Participants emphasises the importance of being attentive and cautious when it comes to how data is handled. They stressed the need to stay informed and in control of data management processes, underscoring the importance of actively monitoring and supervising data handling to ensure it is done responsibly and securely.
- **Theme 3 - Transparency:** Participants acknowledged that transparency is essential in data-related activities, even though it may not always be fully achievable. However, participants agreed the objective should always be to maximise transparency, as it helps maintain the integrity of processes and prevents potential issues associated with incomplete or hidden aspects of data management.
- **Theme 4 - Individual responsibility:** Participants asserted that individual responsibility emphasises citizens' role in society and the choices made. It underlines the significance of personal decisions, such as consumption choices and the data disclosure to government services or the alike. Participants encouraged critical thinking and to not blindly follow 'the herd' but instead making thoughtful, individual choices that align with personal values and the greater good.
- **Theme 5 - Data commerce:** Participants recognise the significant value of data, both in terms of its inherent power and its potential monetary worth. Consequently, they expressed a desire for fair financial compensation from data collectors, as they believe that disclosing individual data should be seen as a valuable contribution.
- **Theme 6 - Choices:** Participants stressed the significance of having the freedom to choose when it comes to sharing data. They expressed a strong desire to decide what data they disclose and the timing of such disclosures.
- **Theme 7 - Consumer profile:** Participants expressed apprehension regarding consumer profiling. They recognised that their purchases are tracked and can be employed to create a consumer profile, which could have both positive and negative implications.

- **Theme 8 - Fallacy:** Participants showed concern about the potential misuse of data, drawing parallels with how "contactless" payment methods can be vulnerable to hacking. They also highlighted the high cost and personal data exposure associated with simplified financial transactions. Participants hoped for better safeguards against data misuse and surveillance, along with clearer choices regarding the personal information that are being collected.
- **Theme 9 – Opportunity:** Participants acknowledged that data is also an opportunity that can be used for good purposes, but also recognizably can be used poorly if ethics are disregarded.
- **Theme 10 - Observation:** Participants mentioned the importance of safeguarding personal information shared and stored online due to the growing prevalence of data exchange. This is considered essential to shield individuals from potential violations or unauthorised access to their personal data.

2.20 PA20: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – EcoTrace

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “**EcoTrace - Empowering Citizens for Sustainable and Nutritional Food Choices.**”

Profile

Project acronym / title	EcoTrace Empowering Citizens for Sustainable and Nutritional Food Choices
Partners (country)	bSPoke Solutions L.P. (Greece); Poios Einai To Afentiko? L.P. (Greece)
Project area	Sustainable Food Systems

Context

EcoTrace is an innovative, data-driven food choice app developed in response to the pressing challenges surrounding food sustainability, data sovereignty, and privacy. The EcoTrace project aims to empower individuals with the knowledge and tools to make informed decisions about their food choices, contributing to more sustainable and healthier food systems. EcoTrace addresses the low readiness level in food and data sovereignty research and intends to foster an improved understanding of data rights while actively advocating for the development of data privacy standards. EcoTrace builds on the EcoSustain platform developed for calculating carbon footprint and sustainability and extends its capabilities further with FOODITY components.

The novelty of EcoTrace lies in its holistic approach to informed food choices:

- **Personalised food and nutrition:** EcoTrace provides personalised food and nutrition recommendations, tailoring dietary choices to individual preferences and health goals.
- **Sustainability insights:** EcoTrace rates food items for sustainability based on various factors and provides a sustainability score for each item.
- **Carbon footprint calculation:** EcoTrace can calculate and display the estimated carbon footprint of food items, considering factors like energy consumption, transportation methods, and emissions during production, **enriching** the existing technology.
- **Traceability function:** EcoTrace uses an event sourcing scheme to bolster traceability within the food supply chain, maintaining an immutable log of all changes to the food supply chain, enabling users to trace the journey of their food from source to table.

EcoTrace aligns with FOODITY's vision: (1) it acknowledges that empowering citizens to take control of their data is a fundamental shift toward better decision-making, promoting healthier food choices; (2) it recognises that better choices are pivotal in steering us towards more sustainable food systems.

Objectives

The main objective of the EcoTrace project is to empower individuals with data for informed food choices, enhancing data sovereignty, promoting food sustainability, and actively engaging citizens. The EcoTrace project will extend and integrate and empower the existing EcoSustain platform with FOODITY components and technologies, and event sourcing scheme technology to achieve a TRL of 7 by the project's conclusion.

Specific objectives include:

- **Developing and integrating the EcoTrace platform**, namely extending and integrating the EcoSustain platform with FOODITY components and implementing event sourcing scheme technology into the EcoTrace platform.
- **Developing data-driven features and insights**, including providing comprehensive and integrated solutions for personalised food and nutrition recommendations, offering sustainability insights, and calculating carbon footprint insights.
- **Enabling traceability and citizen engagement**, by ensuring a secure and transparent ecosystem and engaging citizens in the platform's development and usage.
- **Promoting data sovereignty and sustainability**, particularly increasing citizens' understanding of data rights, promoting sustainability in dietary choices, and validating the EcoTrace platform.

Impact

EcoTrace aims to catalyse a profound shift toward a more sustainable and conscious approach to food consumption. By empowering individuals with personalised, data-driven insights into their dietary choices, EcoTrace will not only significantly reduce the environmental footprint of food production and minimise food waste (indirectly) but also fosters a fundamental transformation in societal behaviour, wherein healthier, more sustainable production and eating practices become the norm. This transformation will transcend individual choices, positively influencing entire food systems, leading to healthier populations, reduced environmental impact, and more transparent, accountable, and sustainable food supply chains, thereby revolutionising the way the world perceives, chooses, and consumes food.

2.21 PA21: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – CSE-TKAS

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “**CSE-TKAS - The Kitchen Adventure: Fostering Behavior Change and Improving Healthy and Sustainable Nutrition Through a Digital App.**”

Profile

Project acronym / title	CSE-TKAS The Kitchen Adventure: Fostering Behavior Change and Improving Healthy and Sustainable Nutrition Through a Digital App”
Partners (country)	MAVAVI 3.0 Kft [Climate Smart Elephant] (Hungary); Stichting International Parents Alliance (Netherlands)
Project area	Food and Nutrition Personalisation

Context

The decline of home cooking is linked with a reduction in fruit and vegetable intake, a rise in ultra-processed food consumption, and a growing prevalence of non-communicable diseases in the EU. Its increased opportunity cost and reputation degradation both contributed to parents not passing on cooking skills to their children, which further accelerated its decline. The dietary habits developed in its wake negatively impact both the environment and consumer health while incurring extra costs on the individual and societal level. This issue needs to be tackled.

The reintroduction of home cooking (especially, of healthy cooking) would address the issue. However, due to its high shadow price and unfavourable reputation, this can be achieved by combining two tactics: (1) pushing for early life adoption, for which parents are the gatekeepers and (2) reframing the activity as a viable fun leisure peer group or familial activity making it quality time and not a chore.

CSE-TKAS builds on the results of an experiment with 160 families that proved that home cooking as a familial leisure activity drives positive behaviour change around dietary choices while increasing environmental awareness. Specifically, CSE-TKAS will develop a digital app that supports healthy cooking skills development outside of such cooking sessions, in an autodidact manner to scale impact.

The novelty of the CSE-TKAS project is related with:

- **Mainstreaming plant-based foods into diets:** combating the visceral opposition to reducing meat consumption, the app mainstreams plant-based foods into everyday diets in small steps, gradually modifying dietary choices through gamification and AI-generated recommendations.

- **Choice management psychology:** acknowledging that having too many choices is detrimental to our desired outcomes, the app intends to present an optimal number of choices each day to facilitate food selection.
- **Gamification:** the app incorporates gamification to engage users and turns meal preparation into a game-like experience. It taps into the motivational psychology that drives video games, incentivizing users to engage with the app and learn new recipes. It also engages children in the process.
- **Data-driven recommendations:** By analysing user decisions and feedback, aggregate taste profiles are created that fuels the recommendation engine along with other criteria, such as seasonality of ingredients, eco-cost, monetary cost. The app makes personalised recipe suggestions that align with the users' dietary preferences, available ingredients, and sustainability goals.
- **AI-driven teaching and recommendation module:** Users can interact with an AI cooking companion that will be able to teach cooking skills and recommend alternative ingredients in case some are missing from the user's inventory. Introducing these digital tools will increase overall digital literacy in the target audience.

Objectives

The main objective of the CSE-TKAS project is to create a "Spotify" for home cooking recipes and cooking skills. The recommendation engine would offer recipes based on aggregate taste profiles, eco cost, seasonality, monetary cost, and would include gamification elements to steer people towards sustainable and healthy choices. The app aims to facilitate the decision of a meal selection and aims to support behaviour change step by step towards healthier and sustainable foods.

Specific objectives include:

- Support parents and achieve FOODITY's mission of innovation and community empowerment in the food and nutrition sector.
- Combat the unsustainable and unhealthy food consumption patterns in the EU.
- Promote plant-based cooking as an essential skill.
- Community involvement and user engagement: involve the industry (plant-based chefs) and the target audience (parents) in the co-design of the app, ensuring it meets their needs and preferences and fosters a sense of ownership and community.
- Business modelling for financial sustainability: build a business model that ensures the app's long-term sustainability, scalability, and inclusion of socially disadvantaged target audiences.

Impact

The project and pilot results are expected to provide a tool to considerably scale up the challenge of behaviour change towards healthier and more sustainable choices. In the long run, the project expects to reduce the cost of involving people in home cooking to a fraction of its current costs and thereby speeding up the process on a European level. The project also aims to build up a taste and food choice preference database that will be indispensable in further nudging endeavours.

The project will demonstrate the app's ability to analyse user data and provide personalised recipe recommendations and by tracking changes in dietary habits, the pilot will showcase the potential for data-driven applications to make a tangible difference in public health and nutrition.

The project expects to demonstrate that this can be achieved with adhering to data sovereignty principles. It will show that data-driven AI and recommendation systems can be trustworthy if the data management is transparent, and if users are offered full control of their personal data and thus, data-driven solutions can be developed and deployed in a way that respects citizens' data rights, which, in turn, helps building trust in citizens.

2.22 PA22: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – DIAITA

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “**DIAITA - Digital diet assistant for cancer patients and their caregivers.**”

Profile

Project acronym / title	DIAITA Digital diet assistant for cancer patients and their caregivers
Partners (country)	Bestiario Proyectos S.L. (Spain); Fundació Alícia (Spain)
Project area	Food and Nutrition Personalisation

Context

In 2020, there were 19.2 million new cancer cases diagnosed globally, with 23% of them occurring in Europe. This number is projected to rise to 30.2 million by 2040, an increase of over 50%. Among these cases, 10% are colorectal cancer, affecting both males and females equally. This highlights the need for reliable dietary guidance to support patients through their unique cancer journeys, emphasising the importance of professional healthcare advice tailored to each individual's specific condition and treatment plan.

In such a landscape, when a person is diagnosed with cancer, they are inundated with a multitude of dietary information from various sources, including websites, blogs, books, and magazines. The accuracy and scientific validation of this information is questionable. Moreover, advice from friends or family, though well-intentioned, might not be universally applicable due to the uniqueness of each patient's condition and treatment. Thus, it becomes imperative for dietary recommendations to originate from credible and knowledgeable sources, ideally the patient's healthcare team.

Furthermore, proper nutrition is a vital aspect of the cancer treatment journey, offering patients the strength and resilience needed to face this challenging period. Recognizing the importance of personalised dietary plans, the DIAITA project introduces an AI-powered solution that integrates an "expert in the loop" approach, ensuring that patients receive customised nutritional recommendations tailored to their unique needs.

At the core of DIAITA is a commitment to empower patients and caregivers by providing them with access to scientific information that underpins each dietary recommendation. This transparency ensures that they are not only informed but also actively involved in the decision-making process regarding their nutritional care. This approach fosters a sense of control and autonomy among patients and their caregivers, contributing positively to their overall well-being.

Moreover, and in line with the commitment to user empowerment, utmost importance is placed on privacy and data sovereignty. The DIAITA solution is designed with robust data protection measures, ensuring that the personal information of our users is safeguarded and treated with the respect it deserves.

The novelty of the DIAITA project is related with the leveraging of an extensive database of recipes crafted and validated by nutrition experts (ALICIA) tailored for cancer patients and annotated according to patients' symptoms, dietary restrictions, and other important dimensions. The inclusion of the “expert in the loop” approach in the recommendation algorithm will ensure that AI-generated meal suggestions are always refined and validated by human experts during the training and tuning phase.

Objectives

The main objective of the DIAITA project is to provide a solution that can assist colorectal cancer patients in achieving and maintaining optimal nutrition. The solution will provide foundational dietary guidelines post-diagnosis and extend specialised dietary advice tailored to specific treatment stages and common associated side effects. It will also offer users access to recipes and dietary plans that have undergone validation by nutrition experts. By leveraging the capacity of Large Language Models (LLMs) and data-driven recommendation engines, the solution will understand user-specific needs and restrictions and relay food recommendations along with clear, concise, and knowledge-driven explanations.

Other specific objectives include:

- Empowering patients and caregivers by providing them with an intuitive tool to access personalised dietary recommendations produced by experts.
- Contributing to the open knowledge ecosystem of FOODITY by including the NAct ontology into an LLM engine and contributing with new open information.
- Pushing boundaries of personalised, explainable and trustworthy AI by providing only information that has been produced based on science and where users can understand why and how recommendations are provided.

Impact

The DIAITA project recognises the importance of a proper nutritional assessment for cancer patients at diagnosis and throughout treatment, as well as combating malnutrition associated with specific types of cancers. DIAITA aims to address this need and existing deficiencies by providing personalised nutrition plans for cancer patients. By incorporating expert knowledge in the fields of nutrition and healthcare, we project expects to contribute to the improvement of the quality of life for cancer patients.

The personalised nutrition plans provided by DIAITA are expected to empower patients to take control of their nutritional health, potentially improving their quality of life. While initially focused on colorectal cancer patients for the pilot, the approach and data ecosystem can be easily extended to cover a range of nutrition needs for citizens with health-related restrictions.

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To facilitate uptake of the results and solution, DIAITA will engage in collaborations with leading medical institutions and organisations to disseminate our findings and increase the visibility of the project. DIAITA will also work closely with policy-makers and stakeholders to advocate for the integration of personalised nutrition plans into cancer treatment protocols, in line with the goals of the FOOD 2030 framework.

Overall, the project is expected to have an impact on the quality of life for cancer patients, ultimately contributing to better health outcomes for this vulnerable population.

2.23 PA23: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – MI4SaferFood

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is **“MI4SaferFOOD - Multispectral imaging application for food safety and quality evaluation.”**

Profile

Project acronym / title	MI4SaferFOOD Multispectral imaging application for food safety and quality evaluation
Partners (country)	Smart Agro Hub S.A. (Greece); Agricultural University of Athens (Greece); Enosi Katanaloton Poiotita Tis Zois (Greece)
Project area	Sustainable Food Systems

Context

Over the past few decades, consumer expectations regarding food quality and freshness have risen steadily. To achieve quality levels that are acceptable to typical buyers, fresh fruits and vegetables sold at supermarkets and other commercial outlets must go through stringent sorting procedures. The quality assessments of fruits and vegetables use colour and other visible characteristics to determine factors such as ripeness, uniformity of shape and size, and absence of defects on skin and flesh. Other assessments look at texture-related features such as firmness, toughness and tenderness. Quality assessments help to decide the appropriate kind of processing and application for each fruit or vegetable, such as peeling, slicing, canning, syrup preparation or raw fruit consumption.

As the demand for food items in both domestic and export markets has grown, automation in the assessment of food quality must go through a process and become a key requirement to help food producers achieve high and consistent quality during both short and long consumption periods; reduce costs; and achieve higher overall supply chain efficiencies, to gain the trust of the consumers.

In the framework of MI4SaferFoods, multispectral imaging (MSI) will be applied, which is a non-destructive technique that can be used to evaluate the quality and safety of the selected fruits and vegetables. Complementing this, the Living Lab methodology will be applied as an open innovation ecosystem focusing on the co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling-up of innovations and businesses. It serves as an intermediary among citizens, research organisations, companies, and government agencies to create sustainable impact.

In MI4SaferFood, the living lab will facilitate the following:

- **Identify stakeholders:** engage with relevant stakeholders such as farmers, agricultural experts, policymakers, and consumers to understand their perspectives and needs.
- **Collect data:** gather data on country-specific crops, food products, climate change projections, and biodiversity indicators. This data can be obtained from various sources such as research institutions, government agencies, and international organisations.
- **Model development:** develop models that simulate the behaviour of crops and food products under different climate change scenarios. These models can be based on existing scientific knowledge and historical data.
- **Scenario creation:** Use the developed models to create five indicative scenarios that represent different combinations of climate change variables (e.g., temperature, precipitation) and their impact on crops and food products. These scenarios should reflect the diversity of country-specific conditions.
- **Validation and refinement:** Validate the model-based scenarios by comparing them with real-world observations and expert opinions. Refine the scenarios based on feedback from stakeholders to ensure their accuracy and relevance.

Objectives

The main objective of the MI4SaferFood project is the application of MSI, a non-destructive technique that can be used to evaluate the quality and safety of the selected fruits and vegetables. This technique captures images using multiple spectral bands, such as visible, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared, and uses the spectral information to distinguish the characteristics and composition of the objects in the images. MSI combines the advantages of spectroscopy and imaging to provide spatial and spectral information about the food product.

Other specific objectives include:

- Identifying the spectral ranges and pics of different food products.
- Developing image processing algorithms for detecting defects or contaminants.
- Establishing a database of spectral signatures for different food products.
- Building a set of recommendations and awareness on how to nudge customers “for safer food safety on-demand”
- Ensuring the awareness of data sovereignty of citizen data during the pilot activities.

Impact

The MI4SaferFood project, focusing on food multispectral image recognition, aims to test the feasibility and effectiveness of using MSI technology to identify and classify different types of vegetables and fruits in Greece. Considering the value of MSI, the project will enable the verification of the hygiene and quality of food products, and estimation of nutritional values and dietary intake of fruits and vegetables, such as calories, carbohydrates, fats, proteins, vitamins, minerals.

Furthermore, the solution will enable consumers to access reliable and transparent information about the origin, freshness, and nutritional value of the fruits and vegetables they buy. A consumer can use the developed mobile application to take photos of fruits and vegetables and instantly monitor their freshness and quality, which will be rated on a 5-star scale. This will help consumers make informed choices and trust the quality of the food they consume.

2.24 PA24: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – STRADA

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “**STRADA - Development of a Miniaturised Food Sensor Enhanced with Data-Driven Technology for Efficient Food Management.**”

Profile

Project acronym / title	STRADA Development of a Miniaturised Food Sensor Enhanced with Data-Driven Technology for Efficient Food Management
Partners (country)	Strada Microsystems (Turkey); EV ILVO (Belgium)
Project area	Sustainable Food Systems

Context

Each year, inefficient food management results in approximately 1.3 billion metric tonnes of global edible food waste. In the European Union, over 88 million tonnes of food are discarded annually. The consequences extend beyond economic losses, contributing to 8% of global greenhouse gas emissions, 20% of freshwater consumption, and 30% of global agricultural land use. Apart from the environmental and economic implications, unsafe food consumption leads to increased outbreaks of food-borne diseases, with an estimated economic impact of US\$110 billion for low- and middle-income economies.

Currently, there is no tool to detect spoilage by the end user right before purchasing the food. Therefore, the primary indicator of food freshness for citizens is the date label, which often provides a conservative estimate with a safety margin.

The STRADA project proposes a food spoilage detector coupled with a smartphone application that can replace the current outdated verification method. The detection mechanism is based on a developed and tested gas sensor that is responsive and highly selective to protein-rich foods. The sensor works seamlessly with beef and chicken and is expected to work for fish and sea-products without further development. Within the scope of FOODITY, the sensor will be optimised to work with fruits and vegetables. The sensor has a 1 cm² footprint, is low-cost, and has a mobile-phone-compatible wireless sensor for rapidly detecting food spoilage.

It comes in two versions - StradaSense (a reusable battery less version) and StradaTrack (battery version) - to tackle the food waste problem. StradaSense can be placed in food packages and with the support of the StradaApp, can allow citizens to identify the days before a food product will become spoiled. StradaTrack is equipped with a battery and can seamlessly integrate into the Internet-of-Things (IoT) systems employed by food producers.

Objectives

The main objectives of STRADA revolve around addressing critical challenges in the food industry. The project aims to significantly reduce food waste by providing individuals with the tools and information needed to make informed decisions based on real-time spoilage data.

Other specific objectives include:

- Enhance health and nutrition by offering personalised meal plans and physical activity suggestions through the StradaApp, encouraging users to adopt healthier lifestyles.
- Optimise cold-chain systems in food-producing companies by implementing the StradaTrack, contributing to increased efficiency, reduced energy consumption, and a lower environmental impact.
- Promoting data sovereignty, emphasising user control and awareness of generated data to ensure a responsible and user-centric approach to information management.

Impact

The STRADA project is expected to promote a set of transformative outcomes. The project offers a transformative solution by suggesting personalised, healthy meal plans based on the products purchased and their respective spoilage levels. This innovative feature not only aids citizens in adhering to healthier dietary choices but also minimises food waste, thereby contributing to improved health and financial well-being.

Furthermore, individuals adopting STRADA solutions are expected to undergo a notable behaviour change, altering their food consumption patterns to reduce waste and embrace healthier choices. In terms of market potential, StradaSense aspires to set a new industry standard, replacing traditional date labels on all food products in stores. Also, the environmental impact is considered to be relevant, as the optimised cold-chain systems and reduced food waste are anticipated to result in decreased energy consumption, a lower carbon footprint, and diminished greenhouse gas emissions, marking a significant stride towards a more sustainable and eco-friendly future.

Lastly, citizens using the StradaSense and StradaApp will possess comprehensive awareness of the data they generate. They retain the full right to choose whether to share this information with governmental and health institutions. Importantly, even if users opt not to permit data sharing, they will still have unrestricted access to all features offered by the StradaSense and StradaApp. This underscores Strada's commitment to ensuring user autonomy and control over their generated data.

2.25 PA25: FOODITY - Open Call #1 project – FoodMarketMap

The FOODITY project launched the first of its two open calls in September 2023 and closed in November 2023. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in January 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is “**FoodMarketMap - Mastering and Recognizing Key Elements of Food Choices to Monitor and Personalise Your Diet.**”

Profile

Project acronym / title	FoodMarketMap Mastering and Recognizing Key Elements of Food Choices to Monitor and Personalise Your Diet
Partners (country)	zerodays, razvoj celostnih programskih rešitev, d.o.o. (Slovenia); Computer Systems Department, Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia); Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University - Skopje (North Macedonia)
Project area	Shopping experiences

Context

The FoodMarketMap project aims to enhance shopping experiences and promote personalised nutrition and sustainable food systems. It empowers citizens through an innovative module within the Eatvisor app, respecting data privacy and ethics while guiding them toward informed, healthier, cost-effective, and sustainable food choices. The new Eatvisor module allows users to photograph shopping receipts, automatically recognizing most food products and their prices by matching them with a food composition database (FCDB). If certain items are not recognized, users can photograph them, and the module employs data-driven food recognition to identify them using the provided images. After each shopping session, users receive recommendations for healthier, sustainable, and cost-effective alternatives.

To implement this module, Eatvisor integrates FOODITY components for food recognition and product identification from photos and develops innovative AI-driven components, including natural language processing for matching products with the FCDB, image-based identification of food logos for evaluating nutritional quality and organic origins, and a recommender system for alternative food choices. Data collection adheres to FAIR principles, utilising the NAct component and other food ontologies for data consistency. FoodMarketMap's outcomes include the Eatvisor mobile app, open-source datasets of shopping experiences, and three additional AI-based data-driven components.

Eatvisor is designed to offer personalised dietary guidance to Slovenian citizens by capturing individual food consumption data (in the form of text or food images) and aligning it with their needs and preferences. The app also facilitates communication with dietitians for professional advice.

Objectives

The main objective of the FoodMarketMap project is to empower citizens by providing a creative mobile app that utilises their data in a secure and ethical way, enabling individuals to make informed, health-conscious, cost-effective, and sustainable food choices. By being more aware of their data and how it will be used, together with insights about data-driven AI solutions, it is expected that citizens' trust in using data-driven digital solutions will implicitly increase.

Other specific objectives include:

- Specifying a detailed plan aligning with FOODITY data ethics for enhancing the Eatvisor app with FOODITY and project-developed AI components.
- Designing a FoodMarketMap module for tracking users' shopping experience, involving 30 end-users.
- Creating supplementary AI components for understanding current diets and providing future food recommendations.
- Estimating the citizens' trust in using a data-driven digital solution for tracking shopping experience and its relation to social innovations such as ethical and sustainable choices, informed decision-making, health and well-being, and technology and social commerce.

Impact

The available Eatvisor app, which will integrate the FoodMarketMap module, will primarily support citizens in making more informed food choices, underlined by secure technical solutions and a comprehensive consideration of citizens' data rights. The extended Eatvisor app will support recommendations for healthy and environmentally-friendly diets and, moreover, will guide users in purchasing food, suggesting new protein alternatives, food made from forgotten crops, local food, food with sustainable and biodegradable food packaging, etc.

The FoodMarketMap project will contribute to a higher availability of shared data for increased competitiveness and sustainability of food system actors. The project will contribute with open-source datasets of temporal shopping experience dataset annotated with a nutritional score, organic characteristics, and prices. The solution will also enable citizens to take control of their food and nutrition data, namely in terms of access, retrieval and consent management.

The data accessible through the FoodMarketMap is expected to offer substantial advantages, extending beyond individual benefits to positively impact the entire food system's value chain. Specifically, insights into shopping habits and detailed information about purchased foods may prove to be valuable resources for food producers, distributors, retailers, restaurants, and caterers, and policymakers. This data empowers citizens in making informed decisions by facilitating food reformulations and strategic choices aimed at meeting consumers' evolving needs, thereby fostering improvements in the food system for both people and the planet.

3 Final considerations

The present document is deliverable D4.8 – “Practice Abstracts – Batch 1”, framed within “WP4 – Outreach and open calls management” of the FOODITY project.

This document includes the **first batch of 25 PA (of a total of 50) that will be developed within the project**. This first batch covers topics such as:

- The FOODITY components
- Information on recommendation systems, datasets, standards, and ontologies
- Information on FOODITY technologies
- The Photovoice engagement activities, and
- The first six FOODITY pilots funded from the project’s first open call

While the 25 PA are presented in this report format, next steps include the preparation of the PA following the EIP-AGRI common format, while maintaining the FOODITY visual identity. These will then be made available on the FOODITY website, Zenodo community and other relevant platforms.

The second batch of 25 PA, to be delivered by the end of the project, will focus on other direct research and outputs of the FOODITY project, as well as the second wave of six FOODITY pilots funded from the project’s second open call.